

L1-Aware Feedback for LLM-Based Language Tutoring: Preliminary Evidence and a Design Framework

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Abstract. Providing feedback on learner language often requires interpreting surface errors whose causes may differ across learners. Many LLM-based tutoring systems can generate grammatically appropriate corrections, but may not explicitly account for whether an error reflects L1 transfer, developmental overgeneralization, or proficiency-related slippage. Using probing classifiers on the ICNALE learner corpus, we find that L1 identity is decodable from hidden representations across three multilingual encoder architectures (peak accuracy 0.71–0.79, chance 0.25). Based on this preliminary evidence, we propose a feedback pipeline that conditions error interpretation and strategy selection on an estimated L1 distribution while keeping uncertainty explicit. This work is presented as a preliminary design study rather than an evaluation of feedback effectiveness; testing whether L1-conditioned feedback improves pedagogical quality or learning outcomes is left for future work.

Keywords: L1 transfer · automated feedback · intelligent tutoring systems · multilingual encoders · probing

1 Introduction

Automated feedback systems for second language (L2) writing have grown more sophisticated, with recent frameworks distinguishing error types and their generalizability to guide feedback strategy selection [3, 12]. However, these systems typically do not account for the learner’s first language (L1) background. The same surface error can arise from different sources depending on L1, and the appropriate pedagogical response differs accordingly. Tense errors, for instance, may reflect the absence of tense morphology in Thai learners’ L1, or a mapping mismatch for Korean and Japanese learners whose L1 marks tense and aspect differently from English. Accounting for L1 background when interpreting such errors can lead to feedback that better reflects its probable cause [3].

Multilingual pretrained language models encode language-specific information in their internal representations [15], but whether L1 identity is recoverable from multilingual encoder representations in a layer-wise probing setting, when processing learner English, has not been directly examined. This paper reports

two preliminary findings and design implications. First, probing experiments on the ICNALE learner corpus show that L1 identity is decodable from multilingual encoder representations across three model architectures. Second, we propose a pipeline in which L1 estimation conditions error interpretation and feedback strategy selection under explicit uncertainty.

2 Background

2.1 Automated Feedback and Error-Type Classification

When a learner writes 'He go to school', a feedback system must decide not just that the verb form is wrong, but what kind of response is appropriate. Explicit rule instruction, indirect elicitation, and contrastive explanation each serve different purposes depending on why the error occurred. Recent work has moved toward error-type classification to support this kind of differentiated feedback [3, 7, 8, 12]. However, surface-form classification alone cannot distinguish errors that look identical but arise from different sources: an L1-influenced error and a developmental overgeneralization can appear the same at the token level, yet call for different responses.

2.2 L1 Transfer in L2 Writing

The need for L1-aware feedback is grounded in the theory of language transfer. Selinker [11] identified transfer as a core process in interlanguage development, separating interlingual errors (L1 interference) from intralingual ones (within-L2 overgeneralization) [2]. This distinction dictates the instructional approach: interlingual errors typically require contrastive explanations between L1 and L2, whereas intralingual errors call for reinforcement of L2-internal rules [8]. For example, verbal morphology omission is frequent among Thai learners due to its absence in their L1, while Korean and Japanese learners show distinct patterns in article and preposition usage tied to native syntactic structures [14].

2.3 Student Modeling in Adaptive Tutoring

Effective Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) rely on student models to tailor instruction to individual needs. While early systems tracked cognitive states through Bayesian Knowledge Tracing [1], recent arguments suggest LLM-based tutoring should incorporate linguistic and cultural backgrounds [9]. Although structured learner modeling improves feedback quality, L1 background remains an under-modeled variable in current generative AI frameworks [7]. Native language identification research has shown that L1 can be inferred from learner text [6, 4], but this signal has not been applied to feedback strategy selection in automated writing feedback systems.

Fig. 1. Layer-wise probing setup. Hidden states are extracted from each layer of three frozen multilingual models. A logistic regression probe (dashed) is trained separately at each layer to predict L1 group membership. The model weights are not updated during probing.

2.4 Probing LLM Representations

Probing classifiers serve as a diagnostic to examine whether specific linguistic properties are encoded in pretrained language model hidden representations without fine-tuning the model [13]. By training a lightweight classifier on frozen hidden states, it is possible to determine if a property, such as a learner’s L1 identity, is recoverable from the model’s internal processing. This work uses probing to provide an empirical basis for the L1 estimation module in the proposed feedback pipeline.

3 Probing Evidence: L1 Signal in Multilingual LLM Representations

3.1 Experimental Setup

We sampled 960 essays from the ICNALE Written Essays corpus [5], balancing proficiency levels (CEFR A2, B1L, B1H) and topics across four L1 groups: Korean (KOR), Japanese (JPN), Chinese (CHN), and Thai (THA). Essay lengths were comparable across groups, with group means ranging from 217 to 233 words. We tokenize each essay using the corresponding encoder’s native tokenizer and

truncate input sequences to 256 tokens. For each layer of each encoder, we extract frozen [CLS] representations and train a multinomial logistic regression probe implemented in scikit-learn [10]. Probes use the L-BFGS solver, L2 regularization with $C = 1.0$, balanced class weights, and a maximum of 1,000 iterations.

Evaluation uses learner-level stratified group 5-fold cross-validation, with folds defined by learner ID so that no learner contributes essays to both train and test. Specifically, we use `StratifiedGroupKFold`, stratifying by L1 label while grouping by learner ID. All random splits use `random_state = 42`. Reported results are means across the five folds. Peak layers are selected based on mean macro-F1 across folds, and the corresponding representations are used in the subsequent error-profile analysis. Random-label and shuffled-feature controls use the same cross-validation splits, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Because minor residual imbalance can arise at the learner-grouped fold level, we select peak layers using mean macro-F1 and report accuracy for comparability with the four-class chance baseline. Subgroup analyses report class-specific F1 because they focus on whether verbal-error density modulates identification of individual L1 groups. As shown in Table 1, random-label and shuffled-feature controls both produced near-chance accuracy (0.243 and 0.221 respectively), confirming that the model representations contain specific structural information for L1 identification.

Table 1. Peak-layer L1 identification performance for each encoder. Layers are selected by mean macro-F1 across five learner-level stratified group folds. Reported accuracy values are means across folds. Chance accuracy is 0.25. Random-label and shuffled-feature controls use the same cross-validation splits.

Model	Peak Layer	Peak Accuracy
mBERT	6	0.789
XLM-R	12	0.738
mDeBERTa-v3	11	0.706
Random label (mBERT)	—	0.243
Shuffled features (mBERT)	—	0.221

3.2 Layer-wise Results

Performance across all models exceeded the chance level of 0.25. As shown in Table 1, peak accuracy ranged from 0.706 to 0.789. The L1 signal emerged during transformer processing, as embedding layer (Layer 0) results remained near chance in all models. mBERT reached peak accuracy at intermediate layers (L6), while XLM-R and mDeBERTa-v3 peaked in later layers (L11–L12). These differences suggest that L1-related information is organized differently across model architectures, but the present experiments do not identify the causal source of the layer-wise variation.

3.3 Error-Type Subgroup Analysis

We examined whether verbal error density is associated with differences in L1 decodability. Thai lacks formal inflectional markers for tense and agreement, unlike the other three L1 groups, which predicts that verbal errors may be more diagnostic of Thai L1. Essays were annotated using LanguageTool and divided into a High subgroup (at least one verbal error; $n = 216$) and a Low subgroup (no verbal errors; $n = 744$).

As shown in Table 2, THA F1 increases in the High subgroup across all three models ($\Delta = +0.012$ for mBERT, $+0.064$ for XLM-R, $+0.209$ for mDeBERTa-v3), while CHN, JPN, and KOR show decreased F1. The consistency of the direction across models suggests that the pattern is not limited to a single architecture, though the subgroup sizes are imbalanced and the analysis should be interpreted cautiously. This pattern is consistent with, but does not by itself establish, the typological prediction that verbal errors are more diagnostic of Thai L1 [14].

Table 2. Exploratory THA F1 by verbal error subgroup across models at peak layer. Δ reports the difference (High – Low).

Model	Subgroup	THA F1	Δ THA F1
mBERT L6	High	0.771	+0.012
	Low	0.759	
XLM-R L12	High	0.688	+0.064
	Low	0.624	
mDeBERTa-v3 L11	High	0.761	+0.209
	Low	0.552	

3.4 Implications for Design

The results above indicate that multilingual encoder representations contain recoverable information about a learner’s L1 background. The probing results indicate decodability rather than causal use of L1 information by the underlying models. The subgroup analysis further suggests that this signal may be stronger in the presence of specific error types, which is consistent with the view that error type and L1 background are jointly informative for interpreting learner production. Section 4 details a pipeline that uses both sources of information to condition error interpretation and feedback strategy selection.

4 Proposed Framework: L1-Aware Feedback Pipeline

We outline a pipeline that incorporates L1 background as a conditioning variable in automated feedback generation for L2 writing. Figure 2 shows the overall

Fig. 2. A simple L1-aware feedback pipeline. Feedback generation is conditioned not on a single fixed L1 label, but on an estimated L1 distribution, allowing uncertainty to remain explicit.

structure: learner input is passed through a multilingual model to produce an estimated L1 distribution, which then conditions both error interpretation and feedback strategy selection.

4.1 Pipeline Overview

The pipeline consists of four stages:

1. **L1 Estimation.** The learner’s L1 is estimated from registration metadata where available, or from representation-based inference using a probe trained on multilingual encoder hidden states. Both paths produce a probability distribution over candidate L1s, and a confidence score is passed downstream.
2. **Error Detection and Classification.** Errors are identified and classified by type using an automated annotation tool, following the typology in [3].
3. **L1-Conditional Error Interpretation.** Each detected error is interpreted in light of the estimated L1 distribution. L1 background raises the prior probability of certain error sources, specifically L1 structural interference, developmental overgeneralization, or proficiency-related slippage, but does not determine them. The interpretation draws on established cross-linguistic patterns [2, 11] and proficiency level as a secondary conditioning variable.
4. **Strategy Selection and Response Generation.** The interpreted error source determines the feedback strategy, which is passed to an LLM as part of a structured prompt following the approach in [7].

4.2 L1-Conditional Interpretation Table

Table 3 lists default interpretations based on documented transfer patterns for the L1 groups in our corpus. These serve as priors that can be overridden by learner-specific evidence such as proficiency level or error history, and are intended to be extensible as additional L1 groups are added.

Table 3. Illustrative L1-conditional priors for error interpretation and possible feedback strategies.

Error Type	L1	Possible Prior Interpretation	Feedback Strategy
Subject-verb agreement	THA	Absent verbal inflection in L1	Explicit rule instruction with contrastive example
Subject-verb agreement	KOR	Proficiency-related slippage	Self-correction elicitation
Article omission	CHN, JPN, KOR, THA	Absent article system in L1	Contrastive explanation; exemplar-based practice
Preposition misuse	KOR, JPN	SOV argument structure interference	Pattern-focused corrective feedback
Tense error	THA	Absent tense morphology in L1	Explicit rule instruction with temporal adverb cues

The same surface error can thus warrant different instructional responses depending on its probable source. A tense error that reflects a structural gap in the learner’s L1 calls for explicit rule introduction, while the same error in a learner whose L1 marks tense differently calls for contrastive mapping. The table makes these distinctions explicit as default priors, not fixed rules.

4.3 Uncertainty Handling

Uncertainty operates at two levels. First, the L1 estimate itself may be unreliable. When no single L1 reaches a confidence threshold, the interpretation stage falls back to a generic error interpretation that does not presuppose L1. Second, even a correct L1 estimate does not guarantee that a given error reflects L1 transfer rather than developmental or individual factors. The pipeline addresses this by preferring feedback strategies that remain informative regardless of the precise error source, reducing the risk of actively misleading the learner in cases of misattribution.

5 Discussion

5.1 Fairness Considerations

Conditioning feedback on L1 group membership introduces a fairness concern. Learners within the same L1 group are not homogeneous: proficiency level, prior instruction, and individual variation all affect error distribution. The uncertainty handling mechanism described in Section 4 partially addresses this by falling back to generic feedback when L1 confidence is low. Beyond the technical mechanism, the system should be transparent to learners about when and how L1 background is used in feedback generation, consistent with calls for explainability in educational AI [9]. From an interface design perspective, this suggests interface elements that allow learners to inspect the L1 estimate underlying their feedback and, where appropriate, correct it, supporting a human-in-the-loop model of L1-aware tutoring. Because inferred L1 background can function as sensitive learner information, systems should avoid using such estimates covertly and should provide learners with control over whether L1-conditioned feedback is enabled.

5.2 Limitations

The probing experiments are limited in scope: the corpus covers four Asian L1 groups and two fixed essay topics, and generalizability to other L1 groups, genres, and proficiency ranges is unknown. The verbal error annotation relies on a rule-based tool that may miss context-dependent cases. The verbal-error subgroup analysis is exploratory and involves imbalanced subgroup sizes, so the observed THA-specific pattern should be interpreted as suggestive rather than confirmatory. The probing results indicate decodability rather than causal use of L1 information by the underlying models.

The proposed framework has not been evaluated empirically. The interpretation table draws on published transfer research but coverage is partial, and some mappings involve post-hoc reasoning. Whether L1-conditioned feedback improves learning outcomes relative to generic feedback remains to be tested with human raters or learner outcome data.

6 Conclusion

Many automated feedback systems apply uniform strategies without explicitly modeling what caused a learner’s error. Probing experiments on the ICNALE corpus show that L1 identity is decodable from multilingual encoder representations across three model architectures, and that verbal error density modulates this signal in a typologically interpretable way. Building on this preliminary evidence, we propose a pipeline that conditions error interpretation and feedback strategy selection on an estimated L1 distribution, keeping uncertainty explicit. More broadly, this work suggests that multilingual model representations may

support uncertainty-aware learner modeling without requiring explicit L1 self-report, though such inference should be transparent and subject to learner control. Evaluating whether L1-conditioned feedback improves feedback quality or learning outcomes in authentic learning contexts is the immediate next step.

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